

INCREASING MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: With the development of society and the growth of production forces, a certain development of the service sector takes place. This, in particular , is the increase in employment in the field, the increase in the technical equipment of labor, and the introduction of advanced technologies.

Currently, the role of the service sector , which is one of the important sectors of the economy , is very large and important. This is related to the complexity of production, the filling of the market with goods based on daily and personal demand , and the rapid growth of scientific and technological progress that renews the life of society.

Key words: Efficiency, efficiency, criterion, efficiency criterion, economic stability criterion, generalizing criteria, specific criteria, quality criteria, management efficiency indicators

Dynamic changes in the market environment, the growth of social uncertainty require constant innovative changes in the management system of economic entities. Ensuring the stability and efficiency of their activities in the conditions of innovative development requires a fundamental change of traditional organizational structures, development of new methods and technologies, and, accordingly, modernization of the management process. This fully applies to the service sector, whose role and

importance is increasing in the process of creating a socially oriented market economy.

Taking place and to create management principles and technologies corresponding to the reality of the changes taking place is the basis of a new organizational rationality. In order for enterprises in the service sector to work effectively, they need a set of management mechanisms and tools that enable them not only to adapt to changes in the socio-economic environment, but also to actively respond to these changes. One of the directions for solving this problem is the use of modern social technologies that help to increase the efficiency of decisions made in management practice and ensure the innovative development of enterprises in the service sector.

A prerequisite for the formation of an effective management system is to change the social methods of managing enterprises in the service sector. The organizational space is manifested as a unique dynamic space of interactions, events, social dimensions, in this regard, in the development of the enterprise management system, a complex system of social coordinates, including the positions of the social space and a certain it is very important to connect to the positions of the organization, its external socio-economic environment. The use of social technologies in management, enterprises, and service industries provide additional opportunities. destructive processes in the organization, and innovative development, the purpose of managing the enterprise in the service sector should be defined on the basis of the need for assistance as a self-organizing system of needs and its capabilities! reveal the relevant human potential and coordinate the intensity and direction of the dynamics of local organizational processes with changes in the socio-economic environment.

Service enterprises based on modern social technologies and the great socio-economic importance determined the main directions of the dissertation research. Currently, in our opinion, a comprehensive approach to the development of human resources is necessary, the quality of which mainly determines the innovative development vector of the enterprise. This requires studying the conditions for the formation of creative motives; behavior of a person, analysis of the subject of innovative activity , internal mechanisms of development of his innovative consciousness, including interests, goals, motives, directions related to the implementation of innovations.

It is necessary to radically change the social technologies used in management practice. The implementation of a strategic approach to the management of the enterprise , the transition to an active social policy model, filling with the new content of social personnel technologies, not only adaptation to external social changes, but also active interaction also contains a secret.

Today, the service sector is considered one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy. The service sector has a solid material and technical base, provides employment to a large number of people and interacts with all sectors of the economic complex, therefore it is the key to the socio-economic development of not only the region, but the entire country. serves as a special catalyst.

The service sector , a set of management mechanisms and tools is necessary, which will enable not only to adapt to changes in the social environment, but also to actively respond to its problems. The use of modern social technologies in management practice by organizations helps to increase the effectiveness of the decisions made, to ensure the innovative development of the organization.

Management efficiency indicators

Management effectiveness is a complex process by its nature. It cannot be represented by only a bit or two pointers . A system of indicators is necessary for this . This system can be divided into two large groups :

- Quantitative indicators describing the operation of the management system, namely:
 - indicators describing the saving of live labor in management;
 - indicators describing the saving of financial resources spent on management ;
 - indicators describing the saving of time spent on management .
- Quality indicators describing the social efficiency of management, namely:
- indicators representing the scientific and technical level of management;
- indicators describing the level of qualification of management staff;
- indicators describing the effectiveness of the decisions made;
- indicators representing the reliability and completeness of information in the management process;
- indicators describing management culture;
- indicators representing the effectiveness of communication;
- management apparatus, etc. Thus, many different quantitative and qualitative indicators are used to evaluate management efficiency. Each indicator should be compared as follows:
 - the real indicators of a certain period with the indicators in the plan and regulations;
 - actual indicators of the current period with indicators of past periods;

- one enterprise with the real indicators of another enterprise. Only then the economic analysis will be carried out both from the point of view of space and time . Management labor efficiency (in one year) is calculated as follows:

$$Jbs = S1/ BX1 : S0/BX0$$

Jbs - management efficiency index;

S0 and **S1** - the result achieved in the base and current periods (gross or product);

BX0 and **BX1** — management costs in the base and current periods.

Annual management costs include the following costs:

- salaries of engineers and technicians;
- material costs;
- Expenditures for the operation of EHM and office equipment; additional and one-time costs (purchase of management equipment and equipment, financing of organizational projects, etc.)

Additional costs:

- business trips;
- transport financing; expenses allocated to the implementation of invention and rationalization proposals;
- consists of costs such as labor protection. One-way costs (**BYX**) are calculated using the following formula:

$$BYX = Xbt + Xii$$

Here:

Xbt - costs for the purchase of control equipment;

Xii - costs for scientific developments, projects carried out to improve management.

Management staff:

- to reduce the level of labor demand of the products produced in the enterprise; to ensure smooth operation of the enterprise;
- to strengthen the material and technical base of production;
- has a great impact on the optimization of the business plan and technical and economic indicators. Therefore, it is very important to determine the management costs (labor) (IT) that are saved due to increased labor productivity:

$$IT_{mu} = J_{mu} : J_{bs}$$

Here:

J_{mu} - labor productivity index;

J_{bs} is an index of management costs.

Savings can also be identified in the management area itself. The following factors influence it here :

- decrease in labor demand among management staff;
- conditional reduction of management staff;
- working time.

mechanization and automation is one of the important directions of improving the enterprise's activity. From this point of view, it is important to determine the cost savings due to the improvement of the structure of the control apparatus. It is known that the lack of personnel also causes great damage to the production process. For this reason, management staff should focus their activities on creating optimal working conditions in the enterprise, properly organizing work, satisfying personal needs, and creating a normal social-spiritual environment in the team.

Methods of calculating the effectiveness of the management system.

To describe the effectiveness of the management system, a general indicator and a group of specific indicators are used. The general indicator is calculated as follows:

$$BTS = \frac{BX_{100}}{AF \cdot K_1 + OF \cdot K_2}$$

BTS - control system effectiveness

BX - annual management costs

AF - main production funds (asset)

OF - working capital

K1 and K2 are the levels of cooperation and concentration (accumulation) of production

$$my \quad \frac{d \cdot mk}{dtk}$$

Here: **K1** is the co-operative coefficient dmk is the weight of co-operative semi-finished products in the value of the product of this enterprise dtk is the weight of the co-operative product in the total cost of the comparable (taken as the basis of comparison) enterprise

$$K = \frac{AF}{mk}$$

index of the management system, the higher the efficiency of the management system, because the lower the cost of management, the higher the labor productivity, the more economical and appropriately managed the production. In order to analyze the effectiveness of the management system in detail, the following system of private indicators is used:

- the coefficient of the ratio of the composition and number of the control apparatus to the norm;
- operative performance coefficient of the control apparatus;
- the coefficient of equipment supply of labor of engineer managers;
- controllability coefficient;
- management coefficient and its execution quality coefficient;
- coefficient of use of mechanization and office equipment in production management ; and others. Measures to improve management provide an opportunity to reduce the management apparatus, compact its organizational structure and increase production volume. The degree of achievement of these results is reflected in the following indicators:
- annual economic effect;
- increase in labor productivity;
- additional capital investment.

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